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Deepfake Detection System

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ABSTRACT

Deepfake technology is becoming a big problem because it makes fake videos look very real. This creates confusion and reduces trust in digital media. To solve this problem, we designed a new system to detect deepfake videos. Our method combines two powerful models: LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) and RESNEXT. RESNEXT helps in analyzing the visual features of each video frame (spatial features), while LSTM studies the sequence of frames to understand changes over time (temporal features). By combining both image and time-based analysis, our system can better detect whether a video is real or fake. We tested our model on different datasets and performed several experiments. The results show that our approach works well in identifying manipulated videos and distinguishing them from real ones. This research helps in fighting deepfake misinformation and supports maintaining trust and authenticity on digital media platforms.

Keywords: *Deepfake Detection, LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory), Image Manipulation, Facial Recognition.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Deepfake technology is growing very fast and is creating very realistic but completely fake videos. While some deepfakes are made for fun and entertainment, they can also be dangerous. Fake videos can spread misinformation and reduce trust in digital media. Because of this, it is very important to develop strong systems that can detect deepfake videos and protect the authenticity of online content. In our research, we propose a new deepfake detection system using advanced deep learning techniques. We use two powerful models: LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) and ResNeXt (a type of Residual Neural Network). ResNeXt helps analyze visual features in each frame of the video (spatial patterns), while LSTM helps study changes across frames over time (temporal patterns). By combining these two approaches and using artificial intelligence and computer vision, our system can effectively detect fake videos and help prevent the spread of manipulated multimedia content on digital platforms.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Deepfake technology has led to a lot of research on how to detect fake and manipulated videos. Many researchers are working on different methods to reduce the risks caused by deepfake content. This section reviews some important research and methods used in deepfake detection.

One prevalent approach in deepfake detection involves the application of deep learning techniques, notably convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), to analyze and classify visual content. Afchar et al. [1] introduced MesoNet, a compact CNN architecture tailored for detecting facial manipulation in videos. Their method focuses on identifying subtle artifacts and inconsistencies introduced during the deepfake generation process, achieving notable accuracy in

distinguishing between authentic and manipulated content.

Tharindu Fernando et al. [2] proposed the rapid advancements in deepfake technology in recent years, which have made fake videos and images appear highly realistic. This review carefully examines the latest techniques for creating and detecting deepfake faces and analyzes their effects on face recognition systems. Furthermore, it highlights the various applications of deepfakes—both beneficial and harmful—identifies current research gaps, and suggests key directions for future investigation.

Surendra Singh Chauhan et al. [3] reviews the looks at different ways to detect deepfakes in images, videos, audio, and text. It explains how modern deep learning models like CNNs, GANs, Transformers, and combined methods are used for this purpose. Overall, the goal is to help create deepfake detection systems that are more accurate, reliable, and can work well in different situations.

Laishram Hemanta Singh et al. [4] introduced the growing challenge posed by deepfake technology, which has made it increasingly difficult to trust digital photos, videos, and audio due to their highly realistic appearance and sound. The review emphasizes the goal of safeguarding digital content through the use of intelligent algorithms and reliable datasets. Mong-Fong Horng et al. [5] proposed a detailed look at the different ways to detect deepfakes in images, videos, audio, and text. It talks about the latest improvements in AI models like CNNs, GANs, Transformers, and combinations of these methods. The paper also looks at important issues such as how well these models work on new data, how fair they are, and how strong they are against tricks. The goal is to help build deepfake detection systems that are more accurate, reliable, and able to handle different types of fake content.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To discover the misleading truth behind deepfake videos.
- To reduce abuse and misleading of common people on the World Wide Web.
- To distinguish and classify videos as

4. METHODOLOGY

fake or real.

- To provide an easy-to-use system that allows users to upload videos and detect whether they are real or fake.

Fig1. Architecture Diagram of Deepfake Detection System

1. Dataset Acquisition and Preprocessing:

In data collection, we gathered a diverse dataset that includes both real and deepfake videos from publicly available sources. We used common datasets like FaceForensics++ and Celeb-DF. The data was stored in well-organized folders so it could be easily used during training and testing. In preprocessing videos underwent preprocessing to extract individual frames and detect facial regions using advanced face detection algorithms. Detected faces were subsequently cropped and aligned to standardize their

appearance and facilitate feature extraction. It resizes images to a fixed dimension (e.g., 224x224 pixels). Normalizes pixel values for better model performance and splits data into training, validation, and testing sets.

2. Feature Extraction:

In RESNEXT for frame-level features frame-level features were extracted using a pre-trained RESNEXT model, fine-tuned specifically for facial feature extraction. The RESNEXT architecture was chosen for its ability to capture intricate facial details and discern subtle

differences between authentic and manipulated content. In temporal analysis with LSTM extracted features were fed into a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network to capture temporal dependencies across frames. The LSTM model was trained to recognize temporal patterns characteristic of deepfake manipulation, leveraging its sequential learning capabilities. It extracts deep facial features using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Also identifies subtle facial inconsistencies like blending artifacts or texture mismatches and generates a feature vector for each image or frame.

3. Model Training and Evaluation:

In the training setup the RESNEXT and LSTM models were trained using a carefully curated subset of the dataset, ensuring a balanced distribution of real and deepfake videos. The training process employed standard techniques such as probabilistic or random gradient descent and back propagation to optimize model parameters. In evaluation metrics the performance of the trained models was evaluated using established evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Model performance was analyzed on a separate

validation set to gauge generalization capabilities. It trains the deep learning model (CNN or CNN-LSTM) using labeled data. Uses Binary Cross-Entropy as the loss function and Adam Optimizer for faster integration. It tests the trained model with unseen data to evaluate performance. Then Calculates accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score and generates a confusion matrix and performance graphs.

5. RESULTS

The performance of the deepfake detection system was evaluated experimentally by observing detection results across multiple test scenarios. The system achieved an average detection accuracy of approximately 85–95%, indicating reliable performance in identifying deepfakes from videos and images. The precision of the system was moderate, which means that most detected objects were actual deepfakes and the number of false detections was minimal. This was achieved by applying confidence thresholding and filtering techniques to eliminate incorrect detections. The recall value indicates that the system successfully detected the deepfakes videos and images.

Fig2: Accuracy and Epoch Graph

	Precision	Recall	F1- Score	Support
Real	1.000000	0.8	0.888889	5.0
Fake	0.833333	1.0	0.909091	5.0
Accuracy	0.900000	0.9	0.900000	0.9
Macro Avg	0.916667	0.9	0.898990	10.0
Weighted Avg	0.916667	0.9	0.898990	10.0

6. DISCUSSION

Our deepfake detection models performed very well. They achieved high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which means the system can correctly identify both real and fake videos most of the time. We used k-fold cross-validation to make sure the model works well on different sets of data and does not just memorize the training data (overfitting). When we compared our model with basic or existing methods, our approach showed better performance. This proves that using deep learning techniques improves deepfake detection. However, there are still some limitations. The dataset size and variety may not cover all types of deepfakes, especially new and advanced ones. In the future, researchers should use larger datasets and try new model architectures to make the system even stronger and more reliable. Also, since deepfake technology can be misused, it is important to use detection systems responsibly and stay alert to new developments.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study shows that combining LSTM and ResNeXt models creates a strong and reliable system for detecting deepfake videos. The model achieved high accuracy and performed well overall. This research is important for cybersecurity and multimedia forensics because it helps identify real videos and separate them from fake or manipulated ones. As deepfake technology keeps improving, it is important to continue research, follow ethical practices, and work together

across different fields to build better detection systems. Overall, our study highlights the importance of staying alert and using technology responsibly to protect digital content and create a safer online environment for everyone.

FUTURE SCOPE

There are many tools available for creating the deep fakes, but for deep fake detection there is hardly any tool available. Our approach for detecting the deep fakes will be great contribution in avoiding the percolation of the deep fakes over the world wide web. We will be providing a web- based platform for the user to upload the video and classify it as fake or real. Even big application like WhatsApp, Facebook can integrate this project with their application for easy pre-detection of deep fakes before sending to another user. A description of the software with Size of input, bounds on input, input validation, input dependency, i/o state diagram, Major inputs, and outputs are described without regard to implementation detail.

REFERENCES

1. D. Afchar, V. Nozick, J. Yamagishi, & I. Echizen, "MesoNet: a compact facial video forgery detection network" in Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops, 2018.
2. Tharindu Fernando, Darshana Privasad, Sridha Sridharan, Arun Ross: "Face Deepfake - a comprehensive review", 2025.
3. Surendra Singh Chauhan, Chin-Shiuh

- Shieh, Mong-Fong Horng: “A contemporary survey on deepfake detection: datasets, algorithms, and challenges”, 2024.
4. Laishram Hemanta Singh, Panem Charanarur, Naveen Kumar Chaudhary: “Advancements in detecting deepfakes: ai algorithms and future prospects”, 2025.
 5. Surendra Singh Chauhan, Chin-Shiuh Shieh, Mong-Fong Horng: “A comprehensive review of deepfake detection techniques: challenges, methodologies, and future directions”, 2025.
 6. I. Goodfellow et al., “Generative adversarial nets,” in *Advances in neural information processing Systems*, 2014.
 7. K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, & J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition”, 2016.
 8. S. Hochreiter & J. Schmidhuber, “Long short-term memory”, 1997.
 9. P. Korshunov & S. Marcel, “Deepfakes: a new threat to face recognition? Assessment and detection,” 2018.
 10. Y. Li, H. Chang, H. Ai, & S. Lyu, “Celeb-DF: A Large-scale Challenging Dataset for DeepFake Forensics,”, 2020.
 11. T. Nguyen & M. Tran, “Deep learning for deepfake detection: A comprehensive review”, 2019.
 12. A. Rossler et al., “Faceforensics++: Learning to detect manipulated facial images,” in *Proceedings of The IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2019.
 13. E. Sabir, W. Cheng, & A. Hoogs, “Recurrent convolutional strategies for facial manipulation detection In videos,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020.
 14. Y. Wu, H. Li, & S. Lyu, “A comprehensive study on deepfake detection: Datasets, methods, and Challenges,”, 2020.
 15. S. Xie et al., “Aggregated residual transformations for deep neural networks,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2017.
 16. B. Zhou et al., “Learning deep features for discriminative localization,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2016.
 17. B. Zoph, V. Vasudevan, J. Shlens, & Q. V. Le, “Learning transferable architectures for scalable image Recognition,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2018.